

RESEARCH ON HO CHI MINH'S THOUGHT ON CULTURE AND VIETNAMESE CULTURAL TOURISM

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Abstract

Ho Chi Minh (1890-1969) was a revolutionary, President of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam from 1945-1969, now the Socialist Republic of Vietnam. Ho Chi Minh's ideology was formed and developed during his revolutionary struggle, including principles, methods, and revolutionary strategies; considered an invaluable spiritual asset, because it brings solidarity, confidence, and direction to the Vietnamese people in building a fair, democratic, and developed society. In terms of politics and law, Ho Chi Minh's ideology is the foundation for Vietnam's current political line. In Ho Chi Minh's ideology, the content of culture is expressed quite specifically, that culture is the spiritual foundation of society; cultural development is associated with the cause of industrialization and modernization; is a part of the industrialization and modernization of the country... Vietnamese politicians and leaders have creatively applied Ho Chi Minh's thoughts, creating momentum for economic and social development, including the field of cultural tourism, becoming one of Vietnam's advantages in developing the tourism economy. This study analyzes some of the main contents of Ho Chi Minh's thoughts on culture and their application in cultural management and cultural tourism development in Vietnam. The author builds a theoretical framework and surveys the opinions of 300 managers of 120 cultural and tourism organizations in several localities across the three regions of Vietnam, including Hung Yen province (North), Da Nang city (Central), An Giang province (South). The results of the research and survey are analyzed and evaluated objectively to draw research conclusions and discuss the policy issues for developing cultural tourism in Vietnam.

Keywords: Ho Chi Minh's thought; Cultural tourism; Vietnam.

1. Introduction

Vietnam marked its independence in the 10th century, and since then, its independent development has gone through many different feudal dynasties. In 1945, the feudal regime ended, and Vietnam continued to develop with a democratic regime, opening a new period of proud history. That long history has created a rich heroic and cultural tradition, giving birth to many great figures. Among them, President Ho Chi Minh is one of the outstanding cultural figures and national heroes, who led the Vietnamese people to independence and freedom.

At the international level, in 1987, at the 24th Session, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) issued Resolution No. 24C/18.65, recognizing President Ho Chi Minh as "Hero of National Liberation and Outstanding Cultural Man of Vietnam". The UNESCO Resolution emphasized the important contributions in many aspects of President Ho Chi Minh in the fields of culture, education and arts, and encouraged member countries to join in commemorating this event.

At the national level, the Vietnamese State affirms, in terms of politics and law, that Ho Chi Minh is the leader of the Vietnamese people; Ho Chi Minh's thought is the foundation for Vietnam's political line. According to contemporary researchers, Ho Chi Minh's thought has great value and an important position for the development and enhancement of Vietnam's position in the Asian region and the world. Because it is the compass for the Vietnamese revolution, the orientation for the cause of innovation and national construction, and at the same time provides valuable lessons on national independence, international solidarity and global integration.

In the cultural field, Ho Chi Minh's thought is the crystallization of Eastern and Western, traditional and modern, national and international cultural values; the personality and cultural mettle of an outstanding cultural figure; leading and orienting the construction, development and elevation of the stature of Vietnamese culture (Nguyet, D.T.M., 2022). With the view that culture is the spiritual foundation of society; cultural development is associated with the cause of industrialization and modernization; is a part of the cause of industrialization and modernization of the country (Quoc, P.V. et al., 2023), Ho Chi Minh's thought on culture continues to affirm its special role and value. Therefore, the study of Ho Chi Minh's thought attracts the attention of many Vietnamese leaders and researchers. And the author's interest in this study is limited to the scope of Ho Chi Minh's ideology on culture and its application in cultural management to promote the development of cultural tourism in Vietnam.

2. Literature review

The 1987 UNESCO honor shows the international recognition of Ho Chi Minh's outstanding contributions to the Vietnamese people and to progressive humanity in the world: National liberation hero, outstanding cultural figure of Vietnam and the world. President Ho Chi Minh's outstanding view on culture is to affirm that culture is the driving force and the goal of the revolutionary cause. Explaining this content, Quoc, P.V. et al. (2023) emphasized that culture, as a system of values that guides the adjustment of the perception, thinking, and behavior of each individual, the whole community and society,

has great power: Nurturing human morality and personality; at the same time, culture is the spiritual foundation of society, cultural development is associated with the cause of industrialization and modernization; is a part of the cause of industrialization and modernization of the country.

On the other hand, Ho Chi Minh arranged the role of culture on par with the political, economic and social fields; considered political, economic, social and cultural factors as pillars of national development (Binh, D.V., 2024). In leading and governing the country, on the basis of Ho Chi Minh's thought on culture, Vietnam has clearly identified the orientation and goal of constantly promoting the cultural values and Vietnamese people, developing culture on par with the economy, politics and society (CPV, 2014; VG, 2023). Accordingly, the Government pays attention to preserving, embellishing and promoting the values of national heritage and culture, tangible and intangible cultural values of regions and areas; prioritizing investment in construction, upgrading and renovation, improving the operational efficiency of the cultural institutional system; Focus on building a culture of healthy behavior in society, promoting traditional values and customs of the nation.

In addition to considering culture as equal to the political, economic and social fields, Ho Chi Minh also emphasized the role of promoting the development of cultural factors, that culture is the driving force for the economic, political and social development of the country; and improving the cultural level of the people is also a necessary thing to build a peaceful, unified, independent, democratic and prosperous country, because when the cultural level of the people is improved, it will help promote the economic recovery and democratic development (NPP, 2011). On this issue, many Vietnamese researchers have explained more deeply and according to Duc, P.D. (2022) and Nguyet, D.T.M. (2022), culture belongs to the superstructure, so it must be based on the construction and development of the infrastructure of society to be able to construct and have enough conditions to develop culture.

In fact, Ho Chi Minh's thought on culture contains many contents, expressing the crystallization of Eastern and Western cultural values, the crystallization of traditional and modern cultural values, the cultural values of the Vietnamese and international people. In this study, the author discusses two main contents: Cultural subject factors (people) and Cultural values. That is the issue of developing cultural people; developing cultural values to promote economic, political and social development. Developing cultural people to realize the goal of preserving and promoting the cultural values of the nation and community. Developing cultural values to affirm the role of spiritual foundation, affirming the role of driving force for economic, political and social development. In the specific aspect of economic, political and social development, the issue of developing cultural tourism is one of the important contents, contributing to national growth. And like other aspects, the development of cultural tourism in Vietnam is affirmed based on the foundation of Ho Chi Minh's ideology on culture, because Vietnam's political line is determined on the basis of his ideology.

In terms of the connotation of cultural tourism, it is a form of tourism related to the participation of tourists in the culture of a country or region, locality, especially the lifestyle of people in those geographical areas, the history of those people, art, architecture, and other

factors that have helped shape their way of life. The development of cultural tourism is associated with the strategic goals of the country and locality, not only in terms of economic development based on the exploitation of inherent cultural values, but also in terms of preserving and promoting cultural values to serve other political and social goals. According to Binh, V.T. (2007) and Bon, N.V. (2020), the development of cultural tourism is a form of tourism development based on cultural values, with the mission of honoring culture and protecting the good cultural values of humanity; At the same time, enriching culture through tourism activities, through cultural exchange, bridging the contact and reception of the cultural quintessence of ethnic groups.

Binh, V.T. (2007) also explained more deeply that developing cultural tourism is not only to gain economic benefits as a business activity but also to have a higher goal, such as contributing to the realization of social development goals, preserving and promoting the value of traditional national cultural heritages, contributing to education, raising awareness of national culture; all the good values of culture through tourism activities can create the most positive development for people and society; material and spiritual cultural heritages are best exploited in tourism activities. Sharing this view, Ha, T.T. (2024) affirmed that developing cultural tourism is a way to enrich from cultural values, while also enriching new cultural values for the treasure of national cultural heritage.

In the economic aspect, the approach of Binh, V.T. (2007) and Ha, T.T. (2024) is reasonable, because when developing cultural tourism, the consumption of cultural tourism products takes place and creates economic value, other cultural values from cultural exchanges between tourists and tourism service organizations and local people. In the cultural and social aspects, the above approaches demonstrate social responsibility when the development of cultural tourism has the mission of honoring culture, protecting cultural values, enriching the culture of the community, the culture of humanity.

It can be seen that, from multidimensional observational perspectives, the above researchers determined the connotation of the "Developing cultural tourism" (DCT) scale to imply the exploitation of cultural values, preservation and promotion of cultural values of the nation and community to promote human development, economic, political and social development of the locality. When placed in the specific context of local state governance, this connotation is expressed in detail, focusing on a number of observational aspects, which can be designed as an observation variable of the scale "Developing cultural tourism" (DCT), that is: Localities exploit the cultural values of ethnic groups and communities responsibly to develop cultural tourism (DCT1); Localities preserve and promote the cultural values of ethnic groups and communities sustainably to develop cultural tourism (DCT2); Localities develop cultural tourism to actively contribute to the implementation of economic and social development goals, and to improve people's understanding and income (DCT3).

In essence, cultural tourism development is based on cultural values, while cultural values contain both material cultural elements (cultural products) and human cultural elements, forming community and national culture. These two elements are affirmed by many studies as constituent elements and conditions for the development of cultural tourism. Duc, L.Q. (2012) emphasized that people and cultural products are the main

cultural resources to promote tourism economic development. Similarly, Hung, T.V. (2024) said that human resource development and cultural product development are important contents to realize the goal of developing cultural resources and promoting cultural tourism development.

Cultural products are defined as cultural values of the nation and local communities (traditional products, folk arts, customs, etc.) that are protected and exploited to become valuable products serving people's cultural enjoyment needs. Protection and exploitation measures are implemented by administrative tools - institutionalizing cultural values; propagating and disseminating cultural values and social awareness and responsibility for protecting, exploiting and promoting cultural values, etc. According to Hang, C.T. (2021), cultural products are very diverse and when preserved, exploited and their values are promoted, they will become important cultural resources for the development of cultural tourism. That requires authorities at all levels to combine exploitation and conservation, promoting cultural values of the nation and community to develop cultural products to serve national and local development goals. The above studies analyze and explain the scale "Cultural product" (CP) when placed in the context of local governance, implying the contents that can be designed into observed variables of this scale, which are: Ethnic and community cultural values are institutionalized to preserve and effectively exploit for the goal of developing local cultural tourism (CP1); Ethnic and community cultural values are communicated to people to raise understanding and awareness, responsibility for protection to exploit for the goal of developing local cultural tourism (CP2); Ethnic and community cultural values are exploited to become diverse cultural products to serve people's needs and develop local cultural tourism (CP3).

Human resources are identified as special social capital and are of great significance to development. This study refers to human resources - cultural people, which are the level, understanding, and awareness of the people - the subjects directly involved in the process of protecting, exploiting, and promoting the value of national and community cultural values in the locality. Many studies emphasize qualities, ethics, knowledge, skills, and aspirations when referring to the development of cultural people. Thien, N.N. (2021) believes that these qualities are crystallized in each person, forming individual culture and community culture. And the requirement for the government is to develop cultural people (propaganda, dissemination of information about national and community culture; education of awareness, responsibility, attitude towards national and community cultural values, etc.), so that each citizen becomes a cultural human resource and a resource for the development of local cultural tourism. With that meaning, the scale "Human resources" (HR) placed in the context of local state governance, is interpreted to imply the contents that can be designed into the observed variables of this scale, that is: People have understanding of community culture, become active participants in the process of developing local cultural tourism (HR1); People have knowledge and skills to protect, exploit and promote community cultural values to develop local cultural tourism (HR2); People have awareness, attitude and responsibility to preserve and promote community cultural values to develop local cultural tourism (HR3).

Through the study of Ho Chi Minh's ideology on culture, the general study of cultural tourism development, the meaning/value of culture is affirmed as the spiritual foundation of society; cultural development is one of the pillars of national development. In a specific aspect, cultural development is the basis for economic development, including the issue of cultural tourism development. And cultural tourism development is formed and directly affected by cultural products and human resources. Accordingly, human resources and cultural products of the community, when preserved and exploited to promote their value, will become important resources for cultural tourism development, contributing to promoting local development goals. With the above explanation, this study puts forward the hypothesis: *Cultural products (H1), Human resources (H2) are important resources, directly affecting the development of local cultural tourism.*

Based on the inheritance and development of the results of many previous studies, the author designed a theoretical research model consisting of 3 scales and 9 observation variables. These observation variables were designed into a survey form with 9 corresponding questions and measured by a 5-level Likert scale: 1 - Strongly disagree; 2 - Disagree; 3 - No opinion; 4 - Agree; 5 - Strongly agree (Table 1, Figure 1).

Table 1. Theoretical framework

No	Scales	Encode	Rating levels				
			1	2	3	4	5
I	Cultural product	CP					
1	Ethnic and community cultural values are institutionalized to preserve and effectively exploit for the goal of developing local cultural tourism	CP1					
2	Ethnic and community cultural values are communicated to people to raise understanding and awareness, responsibility for protection to exploit for the goal of developing local cultural tourism	CP2					
3	Ethnic and community cultural values are exploited to become diverse cultural products to serve people's needs and develop local cultural tourism	CP3					
II	Human Resources	HR					
4	People have understanding of community culture, become active participants in the process of developing local cultural tourism	HR1					
5	People have knowledge and skills to protect, exploit and promote community cultural values to develop local cultural tourism	HR2					
6	People have awareness, attitude and responsibility to preserve and promote community cultural values to develop local cultural tourism	HR3					
III	Developing cultural tourism	DCT					
7	Localities exploit the cultural values of ethnic groups and communities responsibly to develop cultural tourism	DCT1					

No	Scales	Encode	Rating levels				
			1	2	3	4	5
8	Localities preserve and promote the cultural values of ethnic groups and communities sustainably to develop cultural tourism	DCT2					
9	Localities develop cultural tourism to actively contribute to the implementation of economic and social development goals, and to improve people's understanding and income	DCT3					

Source: Compiled by the author through the review

Research model

Figure 1. Research model

3. Research methods

The author uses a combination of qualitative research (collecting and analyzing secondary documents to build a theoretical model) and quantitative research (surveying, collecting and analyzing primary data to test the theoretical model). In quantitative research, according to Hair, J.F. et al. (2009), the minimum sample size required is $N = m \cdot 5$ (in which, m is the number of observed variables). Applied in this study, the model includes 03 scales, 9 observed variables, so the minimum sample size required to conduct the survey is $N = 9 \cdot 5 = 45$.

In fact, the author conducted an official survey with a sample size of $N = 300$ managers of 120 cultural and tourism organizations in a number of localities across three regions of Vietnam, including Hung Yen province (North), Da Nang city (Central), An Giang province (South) ($N > 45$). The survey was conducted selectively to collect information from respondents with experience working and managing in the field of culture and cultural tourism for 3 years or more. The distribution of survey forms was conducted on the basis of preliminary interviews and the consent of respondents; the results obtained 300/300 valid responses, achieving a valid response rate of 100%.

4. Research results and discussion

From the survey data with a sample size of $N = 300$ managers of 120 cultural and tourism organizations collected, the author tested the reliability of the scales and observed variables in the theoretical model. In quantitative research, according to Hair, J.F. et al. (2009), the scales are reliable when meeting the standard condition of Cronbach's $\alpha >$

0.6; the observed variables are reliable when meeting the standard condition of Corrected Item-Total Correlation > 0.3. The test results show that all 3 scales and 9 observed variables in the theoretical model are reliable (Table 2).

Table 2. Statistical results and testing results of the scale

Scales	Observed variables	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation	Cronbach' Alpha	Corrected Item-Total Correlation
1. Cultural product (CP)	CP1	300	1	5	4.02	.715	.687	CP1 = .598
	CP2	300	1	5	3.97	.683		CP2 = .587
	CP3	300	1	5	3.92	.704		CP3 = .602
2. Human resources (HR)	HR1	300	1	5	4.15	.669	.716	HR1 = .601
	HR2	300	1	5	4.22	.711		HR2 = .624
	HR3	300	1	5	4.10	.674		HR3 = .589
3. Developing cultural tourism (DCT)	DCT1	300	1	5	4.04	.644	.704	DCT1 = .619
	DCT2	300	1	5	4.10	.709		DCT2 = .585
	DCT3	300	1	5	4.08	.667		DCT3 = .606
Valid N (listwise)		300						

Source: Author's survey results

The statistical data in Table 2 shows that the observations of the scale "Cultural product" (CP), "Human resources" (HR), "Developing cultural tourism" (DCT) are rated at an average level of Mean ≥ 3.92 , all of which are statistically significant according to the Likert scale (1-5). This shows that the opinions of cultural and tourism organization managers generally assess that localities preserve and promote cultural values, exploit cultural values responsibly to develop cultural tourism, actively contribute to the implementation of economic and social development goals, improve people's understanding and income. National and community cultural values are institutionalized and communicated to raise people's understanding and awareness, and responsibility for protection; exploited to become cultural products to serve people's needs and develop local cultural tourism. People have understanding, knowledge, skills to protect, exploit and have attitudes and responsibilities to preserve and promote community cultural values, becoming active subjects participating in the process of developing local cultural tourism.

In particular, the observed values of the "Cultural product" (CP) scale were assessed at the lowest level with Mean (CP1) = 4.02, Mean (CP2) = 3.97, Mean (CP3) = 3.92, showing that the opinions of cultural and tourism organization managers underestimated the cultural products of localities. That contributed to proving that ethnic and community cultural values were exploited, but cultural products were not diversified to serve the needs of people and develop local cultural tourism; Communication work was deployed, but was not effective in raising people's understanding, awareness and responsibility in protecting and exploiting ethnic and community cultural values to serve the goal of developing local cultural tourism. This issue has a direct impact on the development of local cultural tourism, because when there is diversity of cultural products, when each person is regularly and fully

informed, they will have knowledge and responsibility to protect cultural values, then the locality will have favorable conditions to develop cultural tourism.

The author's research and survey results contribute to reflecting the practice of cultural tourism development in Vietnam, similar to the comments and assessments of some recent studies. Hung, T.V. (2024) analyzed and pointed out the limitations in developing cultural products and proposed solutions to create new cultural products and transform cultural products into products with socio-economic value; at the same time, proposed solutions to diversify forms and methods of propaganda, education, raising awareness and responsibility of people in managing and promoting community cultural values. Similarly, Dong, T.Q. (2025) analyzed the practice and concluded that Vietnam has advantages in developing cultural tourism; however, it has not made a strong impression on the international public, has not created a spectacular breakthrough in developing cultural products.

The scales and observed variables have standard reliability test values, which are the basis for further analysis. The author conducts exploratory factor analysis with Varimax rotation to preliminarily assess the unidimensionality, convergent value, and discriminant value of the scales to have more basis for drawing research conclusions about the suitability of the proposed theoretical research model (Table 3 and Table 4).

Table 3. Total Variance Explained

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.753
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2080.039
	df	36
	Sig.	.000

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.575	39.722	39.722	3.575	39.722	39.722	2.782	30.908	30.908
2	2.829	31.429	71.151	2.829	31.429	71.151	2.714	30.158	61.066
3	1.126	12.506	83.657	1.126	12.506	83.657	2.033	22.592	83.657
4	.493	5.475	89.132						
5	.427	4.741	93.873						
6	.197	2.190	96.063						
7	.171	1.901	97.964						
8	.129	1.431	99.395						
9	.054	.605	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Source: Author's survey results

Table 4. Rotated Component Matrix

Rotated Component Matrix ^a				
Scales	Observed variables	Component		
		1	2	3

1. Cultural product (CP)	CP1	.763		
	CP2	.763		
	CP3	.831		
2. Human resources (HR)	HR1		.869	
	HR2		.863	
	HR3		.789	
3. Developing cultural tourism (DCT)	DCT1			.740
	DCT2			.857
	DCT3			.746
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.				
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.				
a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.				

Source: Author's survey results

In terms of theory, exploratory factor analysis was performed in accordance with the data set shown through the values: $0.5 \leq \text{KMO} \leq 1$; Bartlett test with observation significance level $\text{Sig.} < 0.05$; Eigenvalue ≥ 1 ; Total Variance Explained $\geq 50\%$; Factor Loading ≥ 0.5 (Hair, J.F. et al., 2009). Data in Table 3 and Table 4 show that:

- $\text{KMO} = 0.753 > 0.5$, confirming that exploratory factor analysis is appropriate for the data set; Bartlett's test has an observed significance level of $\text{Sig.} = 0.000 < 0.05$, showing that the observed variables have a linear correlation with the representative factor. Total variance extracted with Cumulative % = $83.657\% > 50\%$ (Table 3), showing that 83.657% of the variation of the representative factors is explained by the observed variables; all observed variables have Factor Loading > 0.5 (Table 4), showing that the observed variables have good statistical significance. The theoretical research model initially proposed is consistent with the survey research practice.

- The observed variables were extracted into 03 factors corresponding to 03 initial factors with Eigenvalues > 1 (Table 3), continuing to confirm the suitability of the initial research model. And the initial research model was kept intact, including: 02 independent variables "Cultural product" (CP), "Human resources" (HR) and 01 dependent variable "Developing cultural tourism" (DCT) with a total of 9 observed variables with good statistical significance, which can perform multivariate linear regression analysis to examine the relationship of the scales in the model. The results of the regression analysis are shown in Table 5, which is the basis for the author to draw research conclusions.

Table 5. Multivariate regression results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.112	.233		12.132	.000	
	Cultural product (CP)	.417	.281	.436	10.216	.000	1.843
	Human resources (HR)	.495	.312	.495	9.247	.000	1.819

a. Dependent Variable: Developing cultural tourism (DCT) R ² : 0.758; Durbin-Watson: 2.008
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Source: Author's survey results

The data in Table 5 shows that:

+ R² = 0.758, confirming that the scales "Cultural product" (CP), "Human resources" (HR) explain 75.8% of the variation in the scale "Developing cultural tourism" (DCT); VIF = 1.843 and VIF = 1.819 ($1 < VIF < 2$), showing that the regression model does not have multicollinearity; Durbin-Watson = 2.008 ($1 < d < 3$), showing that the regression model does not have autocorrelation, confirming that the scales "Cultural product" (CP), "Human resources" (HR) are independent and have the same impact on the scale "Developing cultural tourism" (DCT), confirming the suitability of the theoretical research model with the survey data set.

+ The regression coefficients of the two independent variables "Cultural product" (CP), "Human resources" (HR) are both statistically significant Sig. = 0.000 (Sig. < 0.05) and have positive values: B (CP) = 0.417 and B (HR) = 0.495, confirming the positive relationship between the two independent variables "Cultural product" (CP), "Human resources" (HR) and 01 dependent variable "Developing cultural tourism" (DCT); hypotheses H1, H2 are accepted; the initial research model continues to be confirmed to be appropriate. The multivariate regression model of this study is: $DCT = 1.112 + 0.417*CP + 0.495*HR$. The correlation level of the independent variables and dependent variables in decreasing order is: "Human resources" (HR) and "Cultural product" (CP).

From the above results of inspection, analysis and evaluation, the author's research conclusion is that localities preserve and promote cultural values, exploit cultural values responsibly to develop cultural tourism, contributing positively to the implementation of economic and social development goals, improving people's understanding and income. However, (1) Ethnic and community cultural values are exploited, but cultural products are not diversified to serve people's needs and develop local cultural tourism; (2) Communication work is deployed, but not effective in raising people's understanding, awareness and responsibility in protecting and exploiting ethnic and community cultural values to serve the goal of developing local cultural tourism.

This practical issue has a direct impact on the development of local cultural tourism, because when there is a diversity of cultural products, when each person is regularly and fully communicated, they will have knowledge and responsibility to protect cultural values, then the locality will have favorable conditions to develop cultural tourism. From here, the author discusses policy solutions to contribute to promoting the development of cultural tourism in Vietnam, which are:

- Firstly, localities develop strategies to develop diverse and unique cultural products: (1) Organize research and create new cultural products, creating a connection between tradition and modernity, making the cultural values of the nation and community more unique; (2) Encourage people to collect, create, and promote community cultural products

to supplement the source of cultural products serving the development of local cultural tourism.

- Second, build a communication strategy, promote the cultural values of the nation and community to make those cultural values penetrate more and more deeply into all aspects of social life, becoming the fulcrum and driving force to promote the development of cultural tourism. Because, when each person is regularly and fully propagandized and educated, they will have the understanding, responsibility to protect cultural values, and the locality will have favorable conditions to develop cultural tourism.

Vietnam is in a position to develop and is actually developing at an impressive growth rate; the population has reached 100 million people and people have an increasingly diverse and high-quality demand for cultural enjoyment. This issue is of great significance for the implementation of the cultural product development strategy to create diversity and uniqueness of cultural products, better meeting the spiritual life of the people. Therefore, prioritizing the development of unique, diverse and high-quality cultural products to enhance the cultural values of the nation and community is necessary and meaningful for each locality when implementing the cultural tourism development strategy.

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